

D3.4 Evaluation framework and governance scheme for the final UCs

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¹ PU = Public

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Summary

Begonia Project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced ODPs that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of ODPs across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) UCs, meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

In this deliverable, the monitoring and evaluation plan and the governance scheme for piloting the three final UCs are discussed. To do this, first, the deliverable gives an overview of the project plan for piloting the UCs, considering the project constraints in terms of time and budget for piloting and stakeholders' support. Then, the evaluation and monitoring approach for evaluating the impacts of the proposed solutions from the technical, regulatory, and financial/environmental perspectives is discussed.

Finally, the proposed governance scheme for piloting is explained, considering that the governance of piloting is different from the governance of the detailed UCs presented in deliverable D3.2. The piloting governance is discussed in three aspects of leadership, technical delivery team, and legal and administrative activities.

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Table of Contents

Technical References	1
Document history	3
Summary.....	4
Begonia Project	4
Summary of the Deliverable.....	4
Table of Acronyms	7
List of Tables	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 BEGONIA Project	9
1.2 Work Package 3	9
1.3 Deliverable description	9
1.4 Relation to other deliverables	9
2. The generic approach of piloting the final UCs	10
2.1 Main considerations for defining the piloting approach.....	10
2.1.1 UCs complexities	10
2.1.2 Piloting period.....	10
2.1.3 Stakeholders support	11
2.2 Proposed approach for piloting the UCs	11
2.2.1 Determining the key services to be prototyped	11
2.2.2 Interact with stakeholders supporting the UCs	12
2.2.3 Decision on the services prototyping approach	12
2.2.4 Deployment of services and evaluation of results	12
3. Proposed monitoring and evaluation plan for piloting	14
3.1 Monitoring and evaluation goals	14
3.2 Monitoring and evaluation approach.....	14
3.2.1 Data collection approach.....	14
3.2.2 Monitoring approach.....	15
3.2.3 Evaluation approach and potential evaluation criteria	15
3.2.3.1 Brief description of UCs.....	15
3.2.3.2 Technical evaluation of UCs	17
3.2.3.3 Regulatory alignment evaluation of UCs.....	18
3.2.3.4 financial and environmental impacts evaluation of UCs	20
4. Governance approach for final UC pilots	20
4.1 Leadership of the pilot activities	21
4.2 Technical delivery team of the pilot activities	21
4.3 Legal and administrative matters.....	22

5. Conclusion	22
References.....	23

Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
AFI	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CP	Charge Point
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DGA	Data Governance Act
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ET	Electric Truck
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ODP	Operational Digital Platform
REMIT	Regulation on Wholesale Energy Market Integrity and Transparency
RES	Renewable Energy Resource
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	UC
WP	Work Package

List of Tables

Table 1. Summary of the governance models proposed for final UCs..... 21

1. Introduction

1.1 BEGONIA Project

The aim of the BEGONIA Project is to expedite the European digital transformation by analysing promising solutions and providing recommendations to the European Commission (EC). Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of ODPs in the energy and transport sectors across various European Union (EU) countries, with the goal of facilitating the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2 Work Package 3

Work package (WP) 3 sets the foundations for WP4. The main goal of WP3 is to receive the six shortlisted UCs introduced in WP2-D2.2 [1] and perform the following analyses:

- Design the solution architecture and governance scheme for each UC.
- Develop the necessary regulatory and technical frameworks for each UC and ensure that the selected UCs meet the technical requirements and interoperability standards of the digital infrastructure platform.
- Develop technical, regulatory, and cost-benefit criteria for ranking the UCs.
- Conduct a feasibility study for each UC.
- Rank the UCs based on technical feasibility, regulatory compliance, and cost-benefit analysis, and select the top three UCs and the final shortlisted UCs.
- Finally, defining the monitoring and evaluation plan and the governance scheme for the implementation of solutions.

This way, WP3 will deliver the three final UCs to WP4 for designing specific piloting activities following the main instructions and roadmap for piloting.

1.3 Deliverable description

This deliverable is aligned with Task T3.5 in the grant agreement and the last analysis mentioned in the previous subsection, i.e., defining the monitoring and evaluation plan for the selected UCs and the governance approach for piloting. This requires having a clear idea about the piloting strategy. So, the deliverable first discusses the piloting and prototyping plan, considering the project characteristics.

Then, the piloting governance approach is discussed, and finally, the monitoring and evaluation plan for the final UCs in terms of technical, regulatory, and financial/environmental impacts is explained.

It is worth noting that this deliverable is focused on presenting the approach for each above-mentioned subjects and gives an overview and a roadmap for future activities. Detailed implementations will be presented in future deliverables in WP4.

1.4 Relation to other deliverables

Deliverable D3.4 provides inputs for Deliverables in WP4, including D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3. It gives an overview of the activities in the rest of the project regarding piloting, governance, and evaluation of the UCs.

2. The generic approach of piloting the final UCs

As discussed in the introduction, we need a clear view of the piloting approach at the first step. To this end, in the next subsections, the main considerations for piloting in the context of the Begonia project are discussed. Then, the proposed feasible piloting strategy is explained.

2.1 Main considerations for defining the piloting approach

Piloting the solutions is performed as part of the call requirements, and the goal is to deploy a proof-of-concept testing environment from willing stakeholders to test some of the solutions proposed by the BEGONIA project. The main considerations and challenges for piloting are clarified as below:

2.1.1 UCs complexities

The final three UCs are detailed and complex with various stakeholder involved. Each of the UCI and UCII is the result of merging three other UCs and includes a variety of services (Discussed in deliverable D3.2). In addition to these services, other ODP requirements, such as infrastructure readiness, IoT sensors and smart meters installations, data management, and communication, add complexities to the implementation and deployments of these UCs. Additionally, the three UCs cover three different domains that demand specific attention to each UC.

Furthermore, each service selected for prototyping may involve unique technical constraints, stakeholder roles, and domain/sector-specific requirements. For example, services related to flexibility markets will require interaction with grid operators and aggregators, while services targeting building energy performance might rely more on municipal or facility-level stakeholders. This layering of complexity requires careful mapping of service functionalities to technical environments.

2.1.2 Piloting period

The piloting activities are planned for the last quarter of the project. This gives the project partners a very short period for planning all activities, including making the legal agreements with stakeholders, assessment of stakeholders' infrastructures, determining the installation requirements, procuring the equipment, developing algorithms, deploying services, and finally, evaluation and assessment.

Given this limited window, a mixed piloting strategy is necessary, combining real-world testing with simulated environments. This will allow us to manage time effectively, prioritizing physical deployments for high-impact services with strong stakeholder commitment, while using digital twins and simulators where infrastructure or regulatory readiness is limited.

2.1.3 Stakeholders support

Although the UC topics and offered services are very attractive and interesting for stakeholders and align with their strategies and objectives, the limited piloting period and the level of implementation of solutions, i.e., the proof-of-concept implementation which makes the solutions not very comprehensive and detailed, impose challenges for receiving support from stakeholders in terms of piloting. Additionally, according to the call requirements, the piloting is done with willing stakeholders, and almost no budget is defined for stakeholders for prototyping the solutions. This makes it very difficult to incentivize stakeholders for piloting.

Moreover, stakeholders operate in different regulatory environments across member states, which may affect their ability to support certain services. For this reason, legal and regulatory feasibility must be assessed early on to avoid investing resources in services that may face institutional or policy barriers. Likewise, an upfront technical gap analysis must be performed for each stakeholder to determine whether their existing infrastructure supports the prototyping activities envisioned.

2.2 Proposed approach for piloting the UCs

Taking into account the above explanations, it can be concluded that the detailed and full implementation of UCs with strong support of stakeholders is not feasible. This point has already been foreseen in the call text, and the expectation is to pilot and test the proof-of-concept solutions to the extent possible. So, the piloting will be done by prototyping some of the key features of the UCs at a proof-of-concept level. This means that a simplified minimal function ODP will be developed for each use as a software that includes the key services and all the technical requirements of the ODP in all layers of the proposed solution architecture in Deliverable D3.2. This software will be tested first in the lab simulators to be sure that all the services are functional. Real data received from the stakeholders will be used for modelling the devices and equipment in the simulator and developing algorithms. The work progress and results will be circulated to stakeholders at certain time intervals to get feedback. Some evaluation criteria that are introduced in section 3 will be used for the evaluation of the prototyping. Finally, the developed services in the ODPs are tested in the real-world pilots of stakeholders who are willing to test and use the solutions.

More details on the piloting approach are explained below:

2.2.1 Determining the key services to be prototyped

For each UC, the first step will be to determine which services should be tested. To this end, the key services at each UC are selected for prototyping. The feasibility of implementation based on the stakeholders' support and access to data and expertise will be considered in the selection process. Cross-sector and cross-border features will also be two other factors in selecting the key services.

The selection process also involves evaluating which services provide the highest value for demonstration under the current constraints. Services will be prioritized that (a) test interoperability across domains, (b) challenge regulatory boundaries in a constructive way, and (c) offer clear, measurable outcomes that can be benchmarked in both real and simulated environments.

2.2.2 Interact with stakeholders supporting the UCs

Once the involved stakeholders for each UC are identified, preparatory meetings are set with stakeholders to identify legal requirements, official procedures (templates), timing, technical requirements, and contractual agreements. Additionally, taking into account the key implementation services and the willingness of the stakeholders in providing access to data or technologies, the consortium will conduct a comprehensive review of the available infrastructure, ensuring that the equipment aligns with the project's objectives and regulatory requirements.

This includes a detailed assessment of the existing ICT, metering, and control systems at stakeholder sites. If there are mismatches, the necessary equipment must be identified and integrated into the procurement and purchasing planning. Furthermore, a brief assessment of procurement processes at each site must be completed to ensure the timely acquisition and deployment of necessary tools for prototyping.

Furthermore, a feedback loop is established with stakeholders to receive their feedback regarding the developed algorithms and software.

2.2.3 Decision on the services prototyping approach

The goal of this section is to discuss one of the main concerns of piloting the UCs, i.e., the willingness of the stakeholders to support the piloting. As discussed in section 2.1.3, the stakeholders show limited support for piloting. On the other hand, the consortium is committed to testing the ODP services. In this situation, if we cannot implement a solution in the real world, the only option is to continue with lab simulations and use models, digital twins, and hardware emulators for testing the solutions.

The mixed approach—real-world, where infrastructure, regulation, and stakeholder engagement allow, and simulated, where not—is aligned with best practices in systems innovation projects. It ensures that no service is excluded from validation simply due to deployment limitations. In some cases, hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing or sandbox environments might be used to emulate real deployment conditions.

2.2.4 Deployment of services and evaluation of results

Once the prototyped services, the real world and lab simulation implementation type, and the available infrastructure of pilots are identified, a detailed deployment plan and timeline are defined by the consortium for each UC. This will include the following main steps:

- Analysis of the UCs and determining the technologies and equipment needed for piloting, including whether additional hardware (sensors, controllers) or software licenses are required,
- Procurement of necessary equipment for prototyping, considering the plan for real-world and lab simulation prototyping, and aligned with the procurement procedures of the involved stakeholders,
- Frequent meetings both internally and with stakeholders to monitor the prototyping progress and receive feedback,
- Identifying the regulations that need to be considered in the prototyping of each key service for each UC, especially national data protection laws, energy market rules, and building automation codes,
- Setting the timeline and internal deadlines for prototyping of the services, ensuring alignment with project milestones and stakeholder availability,
- Preparing both real-world and lab simulation testing environments, ensuring real real-life environment check and replicability of test conditions,
- Deployment of solutions addressing interoperability, cybersecurity, privacy, confidentiality, and communication to meet the technical and legal requirements,
- Reporting the prototyping process and assessment of the results based on the framework that is proposed in this deliverable.

3. Monitoring and evaluation plan for piloting

In this section, the monitoring and evaluation framework for piloting the UCs is presented. The goal of designing this framework is to ensure that activities are on track and any issues are identified early (monitoring), and objectives are being met (evaluation). The monitoring and evaluation plan is designed to ensure that each UC is implemented effectively, in alignment with its technical, regulatory, and societal objectives, and that the outcomes can be measured, analysed, and scaled appropriately. To design this framework, we need to determine the goal of performing monitoring and evaluation, determine the data collection approach, set up an evaluation strategy, and define some evaluation criteria for each UC. These requirements are discussed in detail below:

3.1 Monitoring and evaluation goals

The proposed framework should consider the main objectives of the call and the piloting considerations explained in section 2. Reviewing the main call objectives, the main goals of piloting the ODPs can be summarised as supporting the EU environmental and energy targets, enabling a cyber-secure Internet of Energy and an optimised transport system along the major European paths, and optimizing the use of ICT. Therefore, the main objectives of the monitoring and evaluation plan can be listed as:

- Confirming the technical feasibility of implementing and scaling the ODPs
- Checking the compliance of ODPs with EU policies and regulations,
- Highlighting the cost and environmental benefits of ODPs

3.2 Monitoring and evaluation approach

Now, considering the abovementioned objectives, we can define the main framework for monitoring and evaluation. This approach is applied to all three UCs and is led by UC owners.

3.2.1 Data collection approach

One of the key steps in monitoring and evaluation is data collection. Considering the prototyping approach, i.e., real-world or lab simulation implementations, the data collection approach can be different. While meters, surveys, and interviews are the most common approaches to collect data in the cases of real-world implementations, data collected from emulators can be used in the cases of lab simulation implementations.

The data collection plan will rely on both quantitative and qualitative sources, aligned with the technical and business logic of each UC. More specifically:

- Automated data collection from integrated sensors, IoT devices, and APIs (e.g., grid data, EV charging logs)

- User interaction data gathered through the dashboards and front-end interfaces (e.g., booking tools, permit applications, supplier switching modules)
- Backend system logs and analytics for service response time, error rates, and transaction completion
- Stakeholder feedback gathered through structured interviews, questionnaires, and user experience assessments

3.2.2 Monitoring approach

Monitoring is mostly related to the technical and administrative activities during the piloting. This includes the following activities:

- Setting frequent meetings to discuss all piloting activities,
- Ensuring the following piloting activities using the defined piloting approach,
- Ensuring the piloting of the identified key services for each UC,
- Foreseeing the piloting risks and challenges and taking necessary actions,
- Procurement and deployment of equipment,
- Monitoring the legal and administrative activities,
- Determining the time and interval of checking the piloting evaluation criteria (introduced in the next subsection) and performing evaluation analysis,
- Providing standard progress reports,
- Set up regular feedback channels with stakeholders,
- End of piloting review and report based on the evaluation criteria.

3.2.3 Evaluation approach and potential evaluation criteria

Considering the goals defined in section 3.1, the evaluation and monitoring can be performed in three main viewpoints: technical, Regulatory compliance, and financial/environmental. In the next subsections, to make the evaluation discussions more understandable, first, an overview of the UCs is presented. The detailed explanations of each use case can be found in deliverables D3.2 and D3.3. Then, the general evaluation approach of the UCs from technical, Regulatory compliance, and cost/environmental points of view is discussed.

It is worth noting that since the details of piloting plans for each UC, selected key services for piloting, and real-world or simulation-based piloting of the services have not been decided yet, we avoid presenting detailed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and discuss mainly the key evaluation requirements and criteria for all UCs. The KPIs will be presented in the next deliverables.

3.2.3.1 Brief description of UCs

UC1: Electricity customer-centric ODP

The Electricity Customers Centric ODP is designed to place consumers at the center of the energy ecosystem by enabling smarter energy management, market participation, and seamless integration with Renewable Energy Sources (RESs). The platform provides

real-time insights into energy consumption, allowing users to optimise their electricity usage, receive personalised recommendations, and actively participate in demand response programs. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as IoT, AI, and secure data sharing frameworks, the ODP facilitates automated energy supplier switching, supports engagement in virtual energy communities, and enables customers to contribute to grid stability by offering flexibility services. The platform ensures compliance with key EU regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS), while fostering interoperability through standardised data sharing mechanisms like Data Spaces.

The ODP enables two modes of interaction: automated control, where controllable devices such as smart thermostats and batteries respond dynamically to grid conditions while maintaining user-defined comfort levels, and manual control, where users receive notifications and recommendations via mobile apps. Consumers benefit from secure and fast verification processes, transparent billing, and the ability to charge EVs with green energy at competitive prices. Additionally, the platform creates or connects to a local energy market where users can trade power and flexibility services, enhancing the overall efficiency of the electricity grid. AI-driven forecasting tools analyze grid vulnerabilities and help mitigate power instability by leveraging demand-side flexibility. Through these functionalities, the ODP not only enhances consumer engagement but also increases energy efficiency, and promotes sustainable energy practices across the European energy market.

UCII: AI-Driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and grid

The AI-Driven ODP for EV and ET Coordination is designed to address the growing demand for seamless cross-border EV charging and traffic management solutions. With the increasing adoption of EVs and electric trucks (ETs), it is crucial to ensure efficient access to charging infrastructure, optimal route planning, and effective grid integration of RESs. The platform leverages AI-driven analytics, real-time traffic insights, and dynamic pricing models to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of charge point (CP) booking, charging coordination, and grid flexibility services. By integrating historical usage patterns, RES forecasts, and traffic congestion detection, the ODP facilitates data-driven decision-making that benefits commuters, logistics operators, and grid managers. The dynamic pricing mechanism ensures that EVs and ETs are incentivised to charge during periods of high RES production, optimising grid stability while promoting sustainable transport solutions.

The platform supports both private EV users and logistics companies operating large fleets of ETs by offering automated scheduling and fair resource allocation mechanisms. AI-based routing services optimise charging schedules based on real-time grid conditions, availability of renewable energy, and the demand distribution across CPs. The integration with DSOs and TSOs allows the ODP to actively manage grid constraints by leveraging the flexibility of charging stations, mitigating overload risks while ensuring efficient energy

distribution. Additionally, the platform ensures cross-border interoperability by aligning with EU sustainability regulations and promoting standardised data sharing practices.

UCIII: Digitalisation of Data Centres

The Digitalisation of Data Centres for Energy Efficiency and Waste Heat Reuse UC aims to enhance the sustainability and operational efficiency of DCs by leveraging advanced digital technologies. As DCs are among the largest energy consumers, optimising their electricity usage and integrating waste heat recovery solutions is critical for cost reduction and environmental impact. This UC proposes an ODP that enables DCs to function as cross-sector prosumers, participating in the EU energy market while also providing grid flexibility services. Through real-time monitoring, AI-driven analytics, and demand-side flexibility mechanisms, DCs can optimise energy flows, improve cooling efficiency, and support renewable energy integration.

The platform offers two sets of services: DC-related services for monitoring, operation, and planning, and grid-related services for flexibility capacity estimation, computational load transfer, and ancillary service participation. By integrating forecasting models and automated control systems, the ODP ensures that DCs minimise energy waste, strategically shift computational loads across EU member states, and contribute to grid stability. Additionally, the platform aligns with EU sustainability directives by facilitating transparent energy reporting, CF tracking, and regulatory compliance monitoring.

3.2.3.2 Technical evaluation of UCs

This section discusses the general technical criteria for the proof-of-concept implementation of ODP in different UCs. The goal is to cover different technical aspects of the ODP implementation, considering interoperability, scalability, cross-border data communication, integration with data spaces, and so on. The key evaluation criteria are discussed below:

1. Implementation of key identified services of each UC (with minimal reference operation logic needed for ODP to function): It is tested whether the core platform services can operate independently, with minimal integration effort. It checks for the baseline viability of planning and orchestration capabilities across different resources and technologies.
2. Communication to devices and technologies in either the same or a different location, accommodating for local load transfer services: the platform's ability to communicate with and coordinate multiple physical or virtual devices (e.g., buildings, vehicles, edge devices) is evaluated, ensuring local interoperability and operational cohesion.
3. Communication to IoT gateways exchanging either artificial or real sensor/actuator signals: data collection and actuation pathways through the Perception and Middleware layers are tested. Evaluating the success of the ODP in processing real-time or emulated telemetry and sending control signals to IoT-enabled nodes.
4. At least one data spaces connector exchanging data with either artificial or real RES/Grid data/Consumption data through a communication broker according to the data models and connector setup accepted: semantic and structural interoperability

via data space integration is tested. This step confirms that the ODP can access, interpret, and act on external data in line with data space standards.

5. Communication to nodes in two other countries: Testing the cross-border scalability of the platform's communication and governance infrastructure, including the ability to support diverse systems and standards. Also begins to expose regulatory boundaries.
6. A minimal regulatory sandbox setup testing the cross-border regulatory compliance of the deployed operations (with support from the EU parties): the legal and procedural readiness of the ODP setup is validated, ensuring that operations comply with EU and national regulations (e.g., GDPR, energy market rules). Additionally, testing data sovereignty, access rights, and identity management.

These steps allow for testing different aspects of the ODP. The interoperability can be tested by connecting different types of technologies and devices. At the same time, this also tests the scalability of adding said devices. Connecting nodes across countries and using data from different stakeholders ensures that the ODP faces any regulatory constraints. Similarly, for this to be achieved a certain level of governance is needed. All these aspects can be measured and evaluated to determine the feasibility of a full-scale deployment.

The focus of the implementation for each UC is to evaluate the minimal functional ODP to test, in the first place, the operational feasibility is confirmed, and then the setup is applied to evaluate ODP features like interoperability, scalability, regulatory compliance, governance robustness, and identify the gap that has to be eliminated by the full-scale implementation to bring these features in agreement with the stakeholders and regulatory practices. The whole implementation process will be coordinated with the stakeholders for setup validation and gap identification through the monitoring approach defined in section 3.2.2.

3.2.3.3 Regulatory alignment evaluation of UCs

The assessment of alignment with EU regulation focused on how the UCs fit into the broader direction of European policy, rather than checking the current national status in all member states. Since implementation will happen over the next few years, it was more useful to consider future compatibility with European law than to compare national-level regulations, which are often fragmented and slow to adapt.

All three UCs should be aligned with the following key European regulations:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- Data Governance Act (DGA)
- Data Act
- Interoperable Europe Act
- Artificial Intelligence Act

- Electricity Market Directive and Regulation
- Renewable Energy Directive
- Energy Efficiency Directive

UC-specific considerations

UC II (electric vehicles and grid integration) also addresses:

- NIS 2 Directive
- Digital Markets Act
- eIDAS Regulation
- Cybersecurity Network Code
- Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation

UC III (data centres) includes the Regulation on wholesale energy market transparency (REMIT).

It is worth mentioning that since artificial intelligence is used in all three UCs within critical energy and transport infrastructure, parts of the platforms fall under the “High-Risk” category of the Artificial Intelligence Act. This triggers strict obligations for risk management, transparency, human oversight, and cybersecurity, which are being integrated into platform design and monitoring.

Key challenges

Although the ODPs are fully aligned with the European legal framework, putting them into practice in specific countries in a short-term may present challenges. As an example, one key issue is the unclear legal status of the independent aggregator in several member states. This role is essential for providing flexibility services to the grid, but is not yet recognised everywhere, creating uncertainty for the first and second UCs.

The development of energy communities is another area with mixed progress across Europe. In some countries, national laws do not yet support full market participation for these communities, which could limit the potential of the first UC.

Data sharing and interoperability also remain difficult. Even though European frameworks exist, such as the Interoperable Europe Act and the Gaia-X initiative, the technical standards and data-sharing practices are still different from one country to another. This creates barriers for exchanging data across borders and sectors, especially in projects that involve electricity, transport and digital technologies together.

Obviously, these barriers depend greatly on both when the actual implementation will take place and on the countries involved, which will require a detailed analysis that is beyond the scope of BEGONIA.

Piloting

By focusing on long-term regulatory alignment, the BEGONIA project helps ensure the UCs are not only technically and legally sound today but also ready for future European energy and digital ecosystems. However, during the piloting phase, it will be possible to highlight some of the key regulatory challenges that arise from testing certain functionalities of the UCs, even if only in an overview form, and provide feedback for future implementations.

3.2.3.4 financial and environmental impacts evaluation of UCs

Some of the services in the UCs plan to provide energy, cost, and CO2 efficiency services. For example, in UCI, we aim to use demand-side flexibility for energy efficiency, grid flexibility, and supporting renewables. In UCII, one of the objectives is to support renewables using the energy flexibility of EVs and ETs, and UCIII proposes solutions for increasing the energy efficiency of data centres, which benefit both financially and environmentally. In this regard, as part of the evaluation process, the performance of the related services in improving the cost and CO2 efficiency will be investigated by comparing the piloting results and baseline measurements.

4. Governance approach for final UC pilots

The governance models for all the shortlisted UCs have been discussed in detail in Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3. Our previous analysis concluded that governance options vary across different UCs, with varying levels of complexity and flexibility. A summary of these can be found in Table 1. For the UC pilots, the governance approach can be significantly simplified as they consider only a time-limited collaboration with a subset of the stakeholders and a limited scale of implementation.

Table 1. Summary of the governance models proposed for final UCs.

UC	Governance model	ODP ownership	Governance model complexity and flexibility
UCI	Commercial model	Private for-profit	Cross-border virtual energy communities face challenges due to national regulatory barriers Requires multiple national ODP platform instances per member state Complexities in market participation, as not all member states allow independent aggregators
UCII	Commercial or non-profit	Private for-profit entity or public special-purpose vehicle	Both commercial and non-profit models are possible, although the latter is more likely as the market opportunity is niche Strong regulatory environment ideally requires the involvement of regulators in advisory boards
UCIII	Commercial or non-profit	independent private sector entity	Both commercial and non-profit models are possible, although the latter is more likely as the market opportunity is niche Strong regulatory environment ideally requires the involvement of regulators in advisory boards

As the pilot activities take place within the project, they fall in principle under the project's grant and consortium agreement.

Additionally, suitable extensions to these agreements may be necessary to enable the participation of involved pilot stakeholders according to their respective roles.

In the following section, we outline our governance approach in terms of 1) overall pilot leadership, 2) technical delivery and 3) legal and administrative matters.

4.1 Leadership of the pilot activities

While DTU, as project coordinator, manages the entire project, the piloting of each UC will be led by the UC owners, with support and contribution by other consortium partners

DTU is the owner of UCI and UCIII, and BLP is the owner of UCII. UC owners manage all the activities in the piloting process discussed in section 2.2.

The UC owners will allocate tasks and responsibilities to other partners involved in their UC pilot, schedule meetings, and lead the monitoring and evaluation activities for each UC pilot. The UC owners will also lead the preparation of the final reports on pilots in collaboration with all partners and willing stakeholders.

4.2 Technical delivery team of the pilot activities

A group of technical experts in the consortium, which includes WINGS, CDK, and DTU, will manage all technical implementations of each UC under the supervision of the UC owners.

The technical team is responsible for preparing the procurement list for piloting each UC, both in real-world and lab simulation cases. They are the core partners in the prototyping process and develop and deploy all hardware and software solutions. When needed, they will decide to use the expertise of external parties and interact with stakeholders to deal with piloting issues.

4.3 Legal and administrative matters

CEMOSA and OLIVO will handle the legal and administrative aspects of the pilots. Together, they are responsible for preparing the legal requirements, official procedures (templates), timing, safety conditions, and contractual agreements with stakeholders. They will also liaise with the project's Advisory Board and ensure that the board's feedback is taken adequately into account.

Depending on the role of external stakeholders who will participate as pilot partners, suitable pilot agreements will have to be devised in order to ensure that IP is always respected both for the research and development activities related to the demonstrations and for the contributed technology, data, and infrastructure used for the pilot implementations. The IP considerations of the consortium agreement will serve as overall guidance.

Furthermore, the agreements with individual stakeholders to govern the pilot participation will be tailored to the nature of their contributions. For example, for a stakeholder who provides data for a UC pilot, an adequate data sharing agreement will be defined, which governs how the BEGONIA consortium uses this data during the pilot and ensures its compliant use. For a stakeholder that also provides physical infrastructure and assets for the active use in pilot activities, a different agreement may be necessary that also covers restrictions to minimise risks and how to handle physical liability.

5. Conclusion

Deliverable D3.4 provides the monitoring and evaluation plan and the governance scheme for piloting the UCs. In this regard, first, the piloting approach is described. This approach will be followed in WP4 to pilot the solutions and is used to determine the monitoring and evaluation plan and the governance scheme for piloting. In the next step, the monitoring plan was presented, and all the necessary activities for monitoring the successful implementation of the solution were discussed. Additionally, technical, regulatory, and cost/environment evaluation requirements that will be used in the monitoring process were discussed. Finally, the governance of piloting was discussed from the three main points of view: leadership, technical governance, and legal and administrative activities. The key roles and responsibilities of the partners in piloting activities were also determined.

References

[1] Begonia project, Deliverable D2.2, online, available at: <https://www.begonia-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Begonia-D2.2.pdf> [Accessed 26/05/2025]